

Oxidation of Some Hydroxy Acids by Bromine. Part II. The Dark Reaction.

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It has been shown in Part I (previous paper) that citric acid and lactic acid react with bromine very slowly. The reaction between phenyl lactic acid and bromine is fairly large and that between mandelic acid and bromine is quite appreciable. In this paper an account of the influence of potassium bromide and some other electrolytes on the velocity of these reactions has been given. Somewhat similar reactions have been studied by Bugarsky (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, 38, 561 ; 1904, 48, 63) and by Hammick and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2715).

It will be shown later that the negative ions of the acids are alone reactive and hence to study the mechanism of the reaction a constant hydrogen ion concentration must be maintained during its progress. This may be done by the addition of hydrochloric or hydrobromic acid. The diminution in the velocity in presence of the latter acid will be obviously much greater owing to the removal of bromine molecules as tribromide.

TABLE I.

Hydrobromic acid = 0.025M. Bromine = 0.0024N.
Phenyl lactic acid = .05M. Temp. = 25°.

Time in mins. ...	0	60	100	150	230	400
(a-x) ...	9.65	8.35	7.55	6.8	5.2	3.8
k_100105	.00107	.00101	.00102	.00102

TABLE II.

Potassium bromide = 0.025M.

Time in mins. ...	0	30	90	140	230	300
(a-x) ...	9.65	8.35	6.3	5.05	3.35	2.5
k_100209	.00206	.00201	.00201	.00192

Table II shows that the reaction gives practically unimolecular constants in presence of sufficient bromide, thus showing that the rapid fall in the velocity is primarily due to Br-ions. It was thought that the influence of hydrogen ions could be very well studied by adding different amounts of hydrochloric acid ; but quite contrary and unusual results were, however, obtained. The velocity instead of being diminished increased quite considerably.

TABLE III.

Phenyl lactic acid = 0.05M. Temp. = 25°.

Conc. of HCl.	Initial conc. of bromine.	Final conc. of bromine.	Time required to reach the final conc.
0	.00238N	.00065N	150 mins.
.0062M	.00238	.000562	80
.0125	.00237	.000542	55
.025	.00236	.00054	30

TABLE IV.

.00625N-KCl	.0023N	.00054N	60 mins.
.0125N- ,,	.00224	.000545	35
.0125N-BaCl ₂	.0023	.00053	30

It is evident that the increase in the velocity is much greater with potassium chloride than with the same concentration of hydrochloric acid. Similarly the retardation is much greater with HBr than with KBr (Tables I and II). This is due to the influence of hydrogen ions which throw back the dissociation of the reacting acid. Similar results were also obtained in the case of mandelic acid. In this case however, the velocity falls off quite appreciably even in presence of sufficient potassium bromide showing thereby that the influence of hydrogen ions must be also quite considerable. Table V gives the influence of different electrolytes on the velocity of this reaction,

TABLE V.

Mandelic acid = 0.25M. Temp. = 29°.

Conc. of electrolytes.	Initial conc. of bromine.	Final conc. of bromine.	Time required to reach the final conc.
0	0.13M	0.044M	340 mins.
0.0625M-KCl	0.13	0.045	113
0.125M- „	0.128	0.039	90
0.1M-HCl	0.127	0.045	250
0.15M-K ₂ SO ₄	0.127	0.041	160

On the addition of gradually increasing amounts of NaOH to the reacting system which contains KBr, the velocity constant increases regularly. The alkali added forms an equivalent amount of sodium salt which completely ionises, and as the reaction velocity is found to be directly proportional to the amount of alkali added, the negative ions of the acids must be alone reactive. The amount of alkali added was always less than the concentration of the reacting acid so that the solution was always acid.

TABLE VI.

Potassium bromide = 0.05M. Caustic soda = 0.0375M.

Bromine = 0.0024N. Phenyl lactic acid = 0.05M. Temp. = 25°.

Time in minutes.	...	0	10	20	30	40	50	70
(a-x)	...	10.5	7.8	5.9	4.45	3.4	2.7	1.6
k ₁	0.129	0.125	0.124	0.122	0.118	0.117

TABLE VII.

Conc. of NaOH.	κ obs.	k obs./C _{NaOH}
0.125N	0.0425	0.336
0.25	0.0804	0.322
0.375	0.122	0.325

The influence of Br-ions on the reaction might be accounted for by the removal of bromine molecules as tribromide ions, provided

that these do not take part in the reaction. In a solution containing a bromide and bromine

$$k_1 = [\text{Br}^-] \cdot [\text{Br}_2] / [\text{Br}_3^-] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{and } (\text{Br}_2) = [\text{Br}_2] + [\text{Br}_3^-] \quad \dots (2)$$

where (Br_2) and $[\text{Br}_2]$ are the concentrations of total bromine and free bromine respectively. Combining (1) and (2) we have

$$[\text{Br}_2] = (\text{Br}_2) / [1 + [\text{Br}^-] / k_1] \quad \dots (3)$$

If the reaction is due to the free bromine molecules alone then the velocity should be proportional to their concentration at any instant and

$$k_{\text{obs.}} = k_2 / [1 + [\text{Br}^-] / k_1] \quad \dots (4)$$

This conclusion was tested in the following way. The hydrogen ion concentration was maintained constant by the addition of sufficient HBr which also supplied the necessary minimum Br-ion concentration to give a monomolecular constant, and then the concentration of Br-ions was varied by the addition of potassium bromide.

TABLE VIII.

Hydrobromic acid = 0.024M. Temp. = 35°. Phenyl lactic acid = 0.046M. Bromine = 0.00204M.

Conc. of KBr.	Activity of KBr.	Total conc. of Br-ions.	$k_{\text{obs.}}$	$k_{\text{obs.}} [1 + [\text{Br}^-] / k_1]$
0019	.0036	.00458
.0192N	.0171	.0361	.0031	.0047
.0384	.0334	.052	.00264	.00456
.0768	.062	.081	.00209	.00454
.154	.119	.128	.00161	.00456
.308	.222	.241	.0011	.00484

Column 3 gives the total concentration of Br-ions due to hydrobromic acid and potassium bromide. The constancy of values in the last column is quite good. It has been also shown by us in a recent paper that Br_3^- ions are also photochemically inert.

The influence of chlorine ions was also studied exactly in the same way. The concentration of chlorine ions was varied by the addition of potassium chloride.

TABLE IX.

Hydrobromic acid = 0.024*M*. Bromine = 0.00204*M*. Phenyl lactic acid = 0.046*M*. Temp. = 35°.

Conc. of KCl.	Activity of KCl.	k obs.	$k_1 - k$ obs.	$(k_1 - k \text{ obs.})/C_{\text{Cl}}$.
0	—	.0036	—	—
.052 <i>M</i>	.0437	.00642	.00282	.0645
.104	.0826	.00899	.00539	.065
.156	.12	.0118	.0082	.068

In the fourth column ($k_1 - k$ obs.) gives the increase in the unimolecular constant due to the corresponding chlorine ion concentration. The last column shows that the increase in the velocity constant is nearly proportional to the concentration of chlorine ions; it has, however, a tendency to increase. Other negative ions also catalyse the reaction. Thus a 0.083*M* solution of potassium sulphate gave a velocity constant 0.00676. The increase in the velocity was found to be greater with barium chloride than with an equimolecular concentration of potassium chloride.

The activities of the electrolytes have been taken from Lewis and Randall's "Thermodynamics" (1923, p. 362) and the activities of HBr and KBr were regarded as the same as those of HCl and KCl respectively.

For the calculation of the constants given in column 5 (Table IX), k_1 was taken to be 0.07, which is not far different from the value 0.065 given by Jakowkin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1896, **20**, 19) at 25°. Hammick and others (*loc. cit.*) consider the value of k_1 to be greater at higher solutions and obtain 0.07 as the value by plotting the reciprocals of the unimolecular velocity constants against the corresponding bromine ion concentrations. Jones and Hartmann (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1916, **30**, 295) find k_1 to have a value 0.051 at 0°. From Worley's data (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 1107) at 26.5° and the value of k_1 at 0°, Linhart (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **40**, 158) calculates the value of k_1 and finds it to be equal to 0.064 at 32.6°.

which agrees very well with the value obtained from actual experimental data of Worley at the same temperature. In the present case the temperature of the experiments was 35°, so a slightly higher value 0.07 has been chosen. It should be said, however, that slight differences in the value of k_1 will not materially alter the constancy of the results.

A quantitative study of the influence of the various ions on the reaction between mandelic acid and bromine was not attempted. The velocity is very small in presence of HBr at ordinary temperatures. On the other hand at higher temperatures the loss of bromine due to evaporation will be quite considerable. Lactic acid and bromine did not show any noticeable change in the velocity in presence of a chloride.

I wish to express my gratitude to Prof. J. C. Ghosh for his suggestions and valuable advice.

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Received April 10, 1929.
